

Comparative study of thickly polluted pond water of Begusarai district and fungicides and plant extracts on the health of anaerobic bacteria present inside it

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In our environment around them there is nothing safe and sound for use. The air, soil and water and even the edible food grains and other things, they all are highly and badly loaded with harmful chemical compounds which altogether have brought the mankind at dangerous stake. Thus the use of several commercial fungicides in pond water has resulted the disturbance of chemical balance which disturbs the health of different lives residing inside it. Such kind of chemicals are taken by the fishes and through fishes finally we take it and it enters inside and cause different ailments resulting lethal action. In these days there is hue and cry all around, and the World Health Organisation itself has advocated the ban on these chemicals and to find out alternate remedy than it. It will be possible only when we may go through the herbal sources from which it is possible to get the alternate chemical of these harmful commercial fungicides .

Key words : environment, fungicides, edible, harmful, mankind etc.

Introduction : In these days it is the serious situation for mankind to manage their good health in spite of they are living in threatened circumstances engulfing the food items from these polluted ponds and the chemically treated edible items have resulted the different health hazards due to which they have been in the line of danger. The increasing industrialization has changed the life style they altogether are responsible for the pollution of pond water and man himself .

Recently different research programmes are on to find the remedy of such kinds of pollution but no proper methods has been proved successful . If an outlook is given to biotechnological approach then it will be possible to find a new strain of anaerobic bacteria which will be able to consume the hazardous chemicals from pond water and the pond will be safe and sound from being polluted and for which we will go through alteration of genetic setup inside these bacteria to find new strain of recombinant bacteria and it will be possible .

The chemical emitted by different industries and electronic machines disposable materials in the ponds have altered the physical and Fish chemical structure of ponds water and it has disturbed the other living bodies in the nature.

Further the application of different commercially available fungicides on the diseased agricultural plant crops has added to maximum extent in such types of problems. These chemicals when get mixed with the pond water create the serious problem on the health of beneficial anaerobic bacteria responsible for removing pollutants from pond water.

Aims and objectives of Research : The main and important aims and objectives of such types of investigation is to manage good health for human beings and to give a better pathway as a result of which they might be able to their life span. Today activities have created different hardships in environmental systems and due to which there is a danger in front of living things in nature. Generally some people cultivate makhana and waternut crops in pond and if they become infected by fungus, treat them with commercial fungicides.

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Finally these chemicals get mixed with pond water and result water to be polluted. This chemical badly affect health of useful bacteria responsible for consuming the heavy metal mixed with the pond water and responsible for increasing pollution. Whether such types of infected grains will be treated with the plant extracts prepared from different medicinal plants then there will be no use of commercial fungicides and the extracts obtained from natural and herbal sources have no bad impacts on any kinds of living systems.

Thus, it will be beneficial for the health of pond water and due to which the beneficial bacteria will be protected from being exploited and will be able to consume the heavy metals from pond water.

Plan of Work :

-) Medium and Tris-minimal medium (Fasim et.al., 2002)
-) Morphological analysis by gram staining under compound microscope.
-) Survey of Harahi pond and collection of water samples.
-) Isolation of water microbes from each water samples on Pikovskiya Agar
-) Biochemical characterization of isolated anaerobic microbes.
-) Screening of isolates on their nutritional variation in terms of 6 different carbon and 6 nitrogen sources will be applied.
-) Isolation & purification of genomic DNA from isolates and identification of reproductive primers.
-) Elhanol extract of some medicinal plants through soxhlet extractor and rotovapour for the assessment of their antibacterial and antifungal activities.
-) Comparative health analysis of Anarobicbacteria in response to chemical fungicides and medicinal plant extract.
-) PCR Amplification and sequencing of 16Sr RNA gene.
-) Phylogenetic analysis of obtained sequences.

Materials and Methods :

-) For isolation of Anaerobes- Pikovskay's Agar (Hi-medi) & Tris-minimal medium (Fasim et.al., 2002) will be used.
-) Pyrex, corning and borosil glass ware-culture tubes and petriplates will be used throughout the experiment.
-) Merch (Proanalyst) and BDH (Analer)-chemicals will be used throughout experiment.
-) For DNA Isolation : Bacterial & Yeast Genomic DNA purification spin kit (Hi-media) will be used.
-) For PCR Amplification : PCR Amplification readymade kit, PCR Product Purification Readymade Kit (Hi-media) and Primer (G-Bioscience) will be used.
-) The different extracts i.e. cold water, hot water and Ethanol extract will be prepared as per method suggested by Ezhilan et.al.
-) To test the bacterial health different extract will be employed and finally estimated.
-) Chemical fungicide will be applied by food poison technique.

Facilities : The adequate facilities are available in research laboratory, Department of Botany R.K. College, Madhubani and UGC-SAP laboratory, Department of Botany, B.R.A.B.U. Muzaffarpur and Department of Zoology G.D.College, Begusarai, Department of Biotechnology Darbhanga (L.N.M.U.).

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